

Examining the potential of augmented reality to improve health and welfare of animals herded using virtual fencing

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Abstract

Setting up fences and fetching animals is a highly time consuming and labour intensive process. The Virtual Fencing allows farmers to set up a controlled grazing environment. The technology requires animals to wear an Electronic Containment Device which receives the radio signals from the control centre. Whenever the animal approaches the virtual boundary, an audible alarm will be emitted by the device as a cue to avoid further progress towards the virtual fence which may result in a mild electric shock. Even though the technology is promising, there is limited information on how Virtual Fencing affects the behaviour and welfare of the animal. Augmented Reality devices helps to get feel of an imaginary environment augmented to the real one. Combining the Augmented Reality with Virtual Fencing may help to control and herd the animals with a proactive approach. The aim of this trial was to study the responses of an animal to Augmented Reality stimuli and evaluate the potential of Augmented Reality to improve the welfare of animals herded using Virtual Fencing. The Electronic Containment Device fitted to cattle was modified to incorporate some features of Augmented Reality.

Background

It is projected by experts that by 2050, we need to feed nine billion human mouths. Farmers around the world are enhancing the productivity of their farms adopting latest technologies. The last few decades were fortunate for the dairy industry as the milk production per cow has increased. Automated farming technologies have contributed greatly towards reduction of human labour. It is envisaged that getting people to work in the farms will be difficult or will not be economically viable. Reducing the human involvement is a need of the day for any farms. Partial or fully automated systems are available for assisting in the agriculture fields. Increasing the production and reducing the physical involvement of human is a major research area.

The dairy industry is also adopting new technologies like automated paddock management systems and automated herd management systems. Herding the cattle is a very labour intensive activity. Cattle graze over paddocks that are created by the farmers using physical fences. These fences are shifted from one place to another for preventing overgrazing. Installing these fences is a labour intensive activity. Physical fences are static tools which helps to control the animals but without the flexibility of frequent changes in location. Farmers are forced to spent large amount of time and money for installing and maintaining these fences.

Virtual fencing offers the possibility of controlling the animals by implementing an imaginary boundary on landscapes creating virtual paddocks. A virtual fence can be static or dynamic in which the boundary can gradually shift its location as per user instructions. Usually a paddock will be described in the form of a polygon specified by its coordinates. The location of the animal is identified and tracked based on the GPS information usually received from the device attached to the collar. When the animal reaches within the proximity of the fence the virtual fencing device's computer system activate the electromechanical cues that make the animal to alter its direction of movement. The cue is normally a sound stimulus varying in volume proportionate to the distance from the fence and followed by a mild electric shock to keep the animal within the boundary.

Dynamic virtual fences with efficient algorithms proves to be effective and works like the models of herding animals. To herd the cattle the virtual fence moves reactively over time. The virtual fence moves in the desired direction preloaded by the user in the specified time interval. The algorithm should be intelligent enough to avoid the virtual fence from moving into any animal.

We have developed such a virtual herding system and is being used to herd our cows. Even though the system is effective in many situations it fails to provide cent percentage satisfaction. We have noticed that some cows are not reacting to the cues as per our expectation which affects the modelling of the herding process. On few cows the system performed very well and while we conducted the experiments with these cows we could achieve our goal of automated herding.

A challenge we came across during our experiment was the fear that got inculcated in to the animal's memory. The sound cues and electric stimuli is administered to irritate the animal and prevent it from approaching the fence. However it is observed that these physical cues has influenced the behaviour of the cows. Even though it is for a short period of time the heart rate of the cow shoot up following a cue. The frequency of this process certainly affects the stressfulness of the animal. It is a proven fact that low-stress animal husbandry practices are practical and economical. For a cow to be high in milk production we should ensure its well-being. Calm, trusting, cattle are easier to herd and economically beneficial. Administering intensive and horrifying sound cues or electrical stimuli frequently can be painful and would be very detrimental for milk production.

Augmented reality is a technological system that allows inserting virtual contents in the real world in order to run the same representation in real time, enhancing the user's sensory perception of reality. It differs from the conventional virtual reality system in which the user is presented with a completely computer-generated environment. The Augmented reality system applies virtual elements in a real situation augmenting the user's perception of the world. It is a set of techniques that allow adding information to the physical world. Various tools used to create augmented reality environment are computing device, camera, sensors such as accelerometer, GPS, solid state compass etc. the computing devices like smartphone or tablet take the pictures of the surrounding environment through camera and based on the inputs from the sensors the virtual elements are superimposed to the real world.

Figure 1. Description of an augmented reality system

Figure 1 describes the different modules in an Augmented Reality system. The real world environment may have n number of objects. These objects are directly experienced by the user and also captured by the Augmentation Processor. It also receives inputs from different sensors. Based on the real world scenario and the sensor inputs the Augmentation Processor selects the Virtual Objects from the Virtual Object Library. These Virtual Objects selected by the Processor will be merged with the real world environment so that the user gets a feeling that these Virtual Objects are also part of Reality.

The scope of Augmented Reality is very wide and has been used in many fields, such as medicine, entertainment, architecture, education, tourism etc. recent researches [] have shown evidences that Augmented Reality can be an effective tool for treating psychological disorders due to its adaptability to the needs of the patient (even if it differs greatly from reality). The quality and reality of the patients experience in the Augmented Reality system and the emotional engagement it offers could increase its usefulness in psychological disorders treatment.

Adopting Augmented Reality

As we have observed the possibility of using Augmented Reality in treating psychological disorders. We further investigate the possibility of Augmented Reality in increasing the well-being of the animals herded by virtual fences. If we could increase the well-being and reduce the stress it creates on the animals, then we could possibly increase the productivity of the animals and ultimately economic status of the farm. Through an Augmented reality system in the farm the animals feels an environment made up of real elements and virtual elements superimposed over it. The addition of virtual elements may involve view, touch, smell and hearing.

The study was conducted in a farm at Pathanamthitta, Kerala, India. The farm houses many cow-calf pairs. It has a rectangular shaped paddock which was used for grazing of cows. A cow, which was previously controlled using virtual fencing and effectively herded was selected for the study. The daily milk produced by this cow was on an average twelve litres during the milking season. We had observed this cow for two weeks before the virtual herding technique was used on this cow. The average milk production and overall health of the cow was regularly monitored. Then, after two weeks the electronic collar used for virtual herding was tagged to the neck of the cow and was allowed to graze on the entire paddock with certain virtual boundaries.

As an experimental setup, the boundary limits of the paddock was little reduced so that the cow will be approaching the boundary more frequently. It could be observed that it was grazing on the paddock as usual, however with the new boundaries it was receiving frequent cues. Variable cues were administered ranging from a low volume sound to high volume sound and an electric stimuli. The average grazing time per day was eight hours and was between the milking sessions. The cow was milked in the early mornings and late afternoons. The milk production and the overall health of the animal was regularly recorded. After two weeks close observation it could be found that even though the health remains without noticeable change, but the milk production have come down by ten to twenty percentage.

Figure 2. Average milk production with and without the application of Virtual Fence

The reduction in milk production was assumed to be due to the increased stress level of the animal while in virtual herding process. The analysis of the heart beats of the cow adds weightage to this assumption. On a normal condition the heart rate of the cow was fifty to sixty beats per minute. But while an audio cue or electrical stimuli is administered the psychological condition of the animal differs and the fear induced increases the heartbeat rate and the stress. On certain occasions the heart rate seemed to be nearly one hundred and twenty beats per minute.

Even though our algorithm for virtual fencing considers the time interval between electrical cues and allows the animal to come back to normal before any further cues, the average stress level found to be increased considering the entire period of grazing. Every luxury comes with a price. Here the human involvement is reduced by applying virtual fencing, but the stress level of the animal has increased, which will definitely reduce the well-being and productivity. We need to maintain the well-being and at the same time use advanced automation technologies.

The aim should be to avoid the application of scary cues there by avoiding fear induced in the animals. However it is not practically possible always if need to have proper fencing. One solution to this can be having something attractive to the animals within the fence and something non attractive near and on the virtual fence. Since our virtual fence was dynamic, the fencing line will be continuously moving as per pre fed instructions. One condition for the animal being near to the fence is due to the approach of the fence. This can happen if the animal is being there for a long time and the algorithm wants to push the boundary. Here in this situation we exploited the possibility of using the smell as an Augmented Reality Object. As a sound cue we were using the sound of the bark of a dog. The cow was afraid of dogs and its sound work out well in our virtual fencing experiments. We had noticed earlier that even the presence of the dog is irritating to this cow. When the cow is held up in a location for a considerable period and if we need it to move from there, we used to give cues, starting with sound cues at low volume. This may even end up in an electric shock.

To avoid such a situation we tried to create a virtual presence of the dog before sending the bark of the dog as a sound cue to its ears. We did this by spraying a liquid which had the smell of the dog, in the pasture where the cow is grazing. The small container with the liquid was added to the collar of the cow, facing down side. We avoided spraying the liquid while the head of the cow is near to the ground and eating, because it may fell on the sides of it head. Instead it was activated only when the cow held its head straight. With this approach, when we need the cow to move forward, we just drip few drops of this liquid to the ground. In our experiment the cow reluctant to stand in that location after it received the smell and was found to move forward. An attractive area which seemed to be a 'carrot' for the cow could be made non attractive. With this approach we could move the cow without using any cues, not even a scary sound.

Results and discussion

Through this method we were able to move the cow from one location another achieving the goal of virtual herding. Even though mild sound cues were necessary when the cow approached the boundary of the fence, the cow seemed to be calm throughout the day. The heartbeat of the cow was found to be in the normal range. The experiment continued for two more weeks. At the end of the experiment the average milk production data was analysed. The milk production seems to be same like when the cow was left free without any virtual fencing, scary sound cues or electrical stimuli. We could analyse that the cow was calm and free from any stress during our experiment. The wellbeing of the animal could be ensured through our method at the same time incorporating virtual herding technologies.

Figure 3. Comparison of average milk production without the application of Virtual Fence, with Virtual Fence and after adding augmented reality objects

Conclusions

As with all emerging methodologies, virtual herding is in face with challenges. Application of Augmented Reality can help to reduce the ill effects of virtual herding. In our experiment we could achieve the goal of moving the animal from one place to another, keep the animal away from highly attractive source of food which we don't need them to have etc. In a way we could achieve the goals of virtual herding, without making the animal to have stress. The animal could be controlled proactively without using any reactive cues.

Out of many available Augmented Reality objects, we have used only one, the smell. Other sensory objects also could be used effectively. Virtual Fencing and Virtual Herding is a promising technology to cut the cost in dairy industry as it can substantially reduce the human involvement and the cost for installing and maintaining the physical fences, a major element in the expense. A drawback of this is the increased stress induced on the animal. Similar to the virtual fences, adding virtual elements in the physical paddocks can improve the ecological validity of the mixed reality on the animal, augmenting the sense of presence. Augmented Objects which attracts the animal within the boundary and those detracts while approaching the boundary can help to control the animals in a proactive way. Stress free and calm cattle are easier to handle, healthy and can contribute to increase the economic status of the farm.

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